

ACETYLATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF AFRICAN STAR APPLE KERNELS (CHRYSOPHYLLUM ALBIDUM) FOR THE PREPARATION OF CRUDE OIL SORPTION ACTIVE MATERIAL: PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES, FTIR SPECTROSCOPY, AND SURFACE MORPHOLOGY ANALYSIS

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Abstract

In this study, African Star Apple Kernels (Chrysophyllum albidum) underwent acetylation using acetic anhydride under mild conditions, with N-bromosuccinimide serving as a catalyst. This process resulted in the formation of Acetylated African Star Apple Kernel (AASAK). A comprehensive characterization of both the raw and acetylated kernels was performed to evaluate modifications in morphology, surface chemistry, and physicochemical properties. The raw African Star Apple Kernel (RASAK) exhibited a dense structure with limited surface area and a rough texture, characterized by the presence of few visible pores. In contrast, the AASAK displayed a fragmented and flaky structure with larger and more pronounced pores, indicating enhanced surface characteristics conducive to adsorption. To analyze the surface chemistry, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) was employed (using a Shimadzu 8400s, Oxford Spectrometer) to identify unique peaks related to hydroxyl and other functional groups. New spectral bands exhibiting increased frequency and intensity were observed following the modification process, indicating the formation and dissolution of chemical bonds during acetylation. Proximate analysis revealed that RASAK, with a moisture content of 9.74% and an ash content of 2.48%, adheres to the Indonesian Industrial Standard (SII No. 0258-88) thresholds of 15% and 10%, respectively, thereby positioning it as a suitable foundational material for adsorbents. The hydrophobic extractives in the precursor were measured at 14.25%, highlighting its significant potential for crude oil

adsorption. Furthermore, after the removal of extractives, the concentrations of lignin, cellulose, and hemicellulose were determined to be 27.00%, 19.40%, and 24.27%, respectively. The findings of this study underscore that acetylation markedly enhances the structural and chemical properties of African Star Apple Kernels, establishing AASAK as a promising material for environmental remediation, particularly in oil spill clean-up applications.

Keywords: African Star Apple Kernel; Crude Oil Pollution; Remediation; Sorption Active Material; Acetylation; Lignocellulosic Biomass, Biosorbent.

1. INTRODUCTION

Oil pollution continues to represent a significant risk to human livelihoods, soil integrity, and aquatic ecosystems. The exploration of crude oil has resulted in considerable environmental degradation, leading to contamination of air, water, and land resources. Crude oil spills are among the primary causes of contaminated water. The majority of local water bodies is badly tainted with various impurities, featuring both miscible and immiscible oil constituents, as a result of crude oil activities. In addition to harming aquatic life, these contaminants degrade our soil. There is an urgent need to address the economic and environmental effects of oil spills across the oceans and seas [1]. The development of effective and sustainable techniques for petroleum contamination control is imperative due to the frequent occurrence of oil spills, especially in areas that produce oil. Conventional techniques, such as chemical dispersants and artificial sorbents, are frequently harmful to the environment and do not biodegrade. Exploring natural, biodegradable, and affordable materials for oil sorption applications is therefore becoming more and more popular. Lignocellulosic biomass, obtained from agricultural and forestry leftovers, has emerged as a possible alternative due to its abundance, renewability, and biodegradability. There is a chance that oil will spill during production, storage, transportation, and use, which could have a negative effect on the environment [2]. The oil leak is contaminating our health and the food chain. Consequently, if spilled oil is not immediately cleaned up, it poses a major threat to the ecosystem [3]. More people are concerned about oil pollution than other waste or spilled materials, primarily from the sea and navigable water. As oil production has expanded, maritime contamination has progressively increased as well. A total of over 10 million metric tons of petroleum hydrocarbons are imported each year. Conveyance linked events, spills from filling of tankers, and damage of pipelines as a result of process effluents like engine leaks, improper valve usage, and oily waste discharge were the sources of this influx [4]. Pollution that resulted from the effects of shoreline alterations extend to vegetation, marine ecosystems, and beachfront habitats, while also diminishing available amenities. Different hydrocarbons constitute crude oil molecules and they range from light gas to heavy solid. The chemical and physical properties of oil undergo gradual changes when it is released into water. These physicochemical alterations facilitate the disintegration of oil in saline environments [5]. Weathering is the term used to refer to this process which includes dissolution, vaporization, agglomeration, adsorption onto suspended materials, etc. [6]. The negative influence of petroleum leaks around human settings and consequences due to the varying efficacy of oil treatments influenced by factors such as time, oil type, spill characteristics, geographical location, and weather conditions, there is an urgent need for the swift advancement of diverse products designed to remediate oil-contaminated sites. [7]. These materials are primarily composed of Lignocellulose materials, which contribute to their structural integrity and sorption properties. However, the inherent hydrophilicity of these materials limits their oil sorption capacity. To improve the hydrophobic properties and oil affinity of biomass, chemical modifications such as acetylation are utilized. This process involves introducing acetyl groups to the hydroxyl sites within the biomass, which reduces its polarity and enhances its hydrophobic characteristics. As a result, the material's ability to interact with non-polar substances, such as oil, is significantly improved, thus increasing its sorption capacity. Furthermore, acetylation can also modify

the surface morphology and enhance the porosity of the biomass, contributing further to its efficiency in oil sorption [8]. In West Africa, the African Star Apple (*Chrysophyllum albidum*) is widely consumed, reflecting its popularity as a tropical fruit in the region and belongs to the family Sapotaceae, which is classified under the order Ericales. This plant family encompasses seventy genera and eight hundred species. Each of the specie produces milky latex [9]. Twenty-three (23) genera and over three hundred (300) species are found in West Africa including *Chrysophyllum*, *Kanton*, *Mimusops*, *Breviea*, *Delipdora* and *Manikara* [9]. Nigeria has seven (7) of the species including *Albidum* and *Africanum*. The name *Chrysophyllum* is coined from the Greek word for “Golden leaf” which depicts the colour of the leaves of some of its species. The African Star Apple fruit has gained popularity and is widely consumed because of its fleshy pulp but the seeds are discard. Its common name in Nigeria include cherry, agbalumo (Yoruba), udara (Ibo) and ehya (Igala) [10]. The Star Apple of Africa (*Chrysophyllum alb*) is endearingly known as Agwaluma among the Hausa people and is referred to as Alasa in Ghana. In Benin, a neighboring nation, various dialects give this fruit distinct names, including azongogwe or azonbobwe, Fon or Goun, alongside azonvivo or azonvovwe, and azonbebi. In the West African region, idum is a widely consumed tropical fruit [11]. In Nigeria, the fruits initially appear as dark green spheres on the tree in July, gradually transitioning to shades of yellow or orange. Local knowledge indicates that yellow fruits yield sweet pulp, while those exhibiting a blend of green and yellow tend to produce a bitter taste. The most desirable variety among these is the orange-colored fruit. The ripe fruit can be found in the market between December to March. Yearly, a huge amount of the fruit is lost due to deterioration during gathering, transportation and storage. The deterioration of the pulp begins after about five days under ambient conditions and also investigated the use of the fruit as drinks and jams to mitigate the yearly loss. The plant, commonly found in Central, Eastern and West Africa is about 8 to 36 metres tall. It is commonly propagated by its seedlings, wildings and by direct sowing. African Star Apple tree has evergreen leaves which are elliptic, slightly leathery and alternate. The fruit usually has five central radially-arranged seeds. When the fruit is cut transversely, the seeds section appears as a star hence the name Star Apple [10]. The specie *Chrysophyllum Africanum* is widely distributed in West and Central Africa and usually found on riverside, in forest and villages. Its wood has fine to medium grain texture [12]. Another member of the family *Chrysophyllum Oliviforme* commonly found in Florida (USA) grows up to 14 meters and can spread to 8 meters across. Possessing 4-inch long glossy dark green leaves, satinleaf as it is popularly called, remains evergreen like the *Chysophyllum Albidum* and *Chrysophyllum Africanum*. Its fruits are however long and oval [13]. The seeds, often discarded as waste, represent a potential source of lignocellulosic biomass. Utilizing these kernels not only adds value to agricultural waste but also aligns with sustainable waste management practices. Preliminary studies suggest that the kernels possess a significant amount of cellulose and lignin, making them suitable candidates for chemical modification and subsequent application in oil sorption. The biodegradable properties of organic sorbents sourced from plants ensure that they leave no enduring residue. Agricultural process residues can be characterized as polymeric composites predominantly made up of cellulose, hemicelluloses, and lignin [14]. These polymers significantly influence the chemical and physical properties of the materials, as they form the structural components of the cell wall [15]. Furthermore, organic sorbents derived from ants are biodegradable, ensuring that they do not leave a lasting environmental impact. While various lignocellulosic materials have been explored for oil sorption applications, there is limited research on the utilization of African Star Apple Kernels. The various forms of pollution resulting from oil spills pose significant threats to human health, wildlife, and plant life. Given the detrimental impacts on ecosystems and the potential for long-term environmental damage, it is crucial to develop a range of materials for effectively removing oil from affected areas. Several factors have highlighted the necessity of this research: the non-biodegradability of imported sorbent materials, which intensifies environmental pollution; the lack of natural, cost-effective, and biodegradable alternatives to synthetic sorbents; the degradation

of fertile agricultural land and marine habitats due to oil spills; and the well-documented challenges associated with water sorption and dimensional stability in agricultural by-products, which are influenced by their inherent hydroxyl activity; Crude oil pollution significantly diminishes both domestic usage and export volumes, adversely affecting tourism, leisure activities, and the overall economy. Furthermore, the escalating expenses associated with imported synthetic sorbent materials contribute to heightened costs of oil cleanup operations.

In several regions of Nigeria, particularly those engaged in petroleum extraction activities, many water bodies are significantly polluted with oil. This contamination results from unintended spills that occur during extraction, distribution, storage, or use as well as from acts of pipeline vandalism. The resulting oil spills pose a grave threat to the local ecosystem, jeopardizing both human health and marine life. Furthermore, the remediation methods employed by oil companies often prove inadequate or, in some cases, detrimental to aquatic organisms, thereby affecting the overall food chain. Therefore, it is essential to develop and implement a variety of effective cleanup materials for areas impacted by oil contamination [16]. Investigating the acetylation of these kernels and understanding the resultant changes in their physicochemical properties can provide insights into their potential as effective oil sorbents. This study seeks to chemically modify Raw African Star Apple Kernels (RASAK) through acetylation with acetic anhydride in the presence of N-bromosuccinimide as a catalyst. We will utilize advanced characterization techniques, namely Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), to analyze both raw and acetylated kernels (AASAK). This analysis will help identify shifts in functional groups and surface morphology, thereby providing insights into the structural and chemical changes that enhance their sorption capabilities. Additionally, we will evaluate the physicochemical properties of the kernels, such as moisture content, ash content, and lignocellulosic composition. The potential of the acetylated kernels in crude oil sorption applications will also be assessed. The outcomes of this research could significantly advance the development of sustainable and efficient oil sorbents from agricultural waste. By maximizing the value of African Star Apple Kernels, this study aims to promote environmental sustainability while offering a cost-effective solution for addressing oil spill remediation challenges.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Reagents and Materials

All reagents utilized in this study were of analytical grade and were employed without any further purification. The chemicals included ethanol (Sigma-Aldrich; CAS No. 64-17-5), n-hexane (Merck Millipore; CAS No. 110-54-3), acetic anhydride (Sigma-Aldrich; CAS No. 108-24-7), N-bromosuccinimide (Sigma-Aldrich; CAS No. 128-08-5), and acetone (BDH; CAS No. 67-64-1).

The materials employed included African Star Apple Seeds (ASAS) and crude oil. Instruments used in the study comprised a steam bath, heating mantle, analytical balance, drying oven, muffle furnace, and a digital rotary viscometer (NDJ-85). Additional equipment for characterization and analysis included a condenser, a Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrometer (Shimadzu 8400s, Spectrometer, Oxford), and a Scanning Electron Microscope (Phenom-World).

Sample Collection

Mature seeds of the African Star Apple (*Chrysophyllum albidum*) were procured from a local market in Awka, located in the Anambra state of Nigeria. A crude oil sample was obtained from a neighborhood market in Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria. This sample was provided by the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC) based in Port Harcourt, Rivers State.

Sample Preparation

The African Star Apple seeds were meticulously cleaned through several rounds of washing with distilled water to effectively eliminate dirt, fungi, and other surface contaminants, as well as any water-soluble impurities. After thorough cleaning, the seeds were sun-dried for five hours each day over a period of four consecutive days. Subsequently, they underwent further drying, the samples were placed in a laboratory oven maintained at a temperature of 65 °C for a duration of 24 hours to ensure the complete elimination of any residual moisture. Once adequately dried, the seeds were dehulled and pulverized, then sifted through 20 and 25 British Standard Sieves (BSS) to ensure uniform particle sizes. The processed samples were subsequently stored in airtight containers at room temperature until they were needed for analysis.

Acetylation of ASAK

The acetylation process of the pulverized African Star Apple Kernel (ASAK) was conducted to modify its surface properties and enhance its oil sorption capacity. Following the guidelines stipulated by [17] An amount of approximately 20 g of dried and sieved ASAK was measured and placed into a 250 mL round-bottom flask. Subsequently, 100 mL of acetic anhydride was added as the acetylating agent, with the reaction being catalyzed by the introduction of 0.5 g of N-bromosuccinimide (NBS). The mixture was subjected to stirring and mild reflux heating at a temperature range of 60–70°C for a duration of 90 minutes. Following the completion of the reaction, the acetylated product was allowed to cool to room temperature and then thoroughly washed with distilled water and acetone to eliminate any residual reagents and by-products. The material, now designated as Acetylated African Star Apple Kernel (AASAK), was subsequently dried in an oven at 65°C for 12 hours and stored in an airtight container for future analysis.

FTIR of RASAK and AASAK

FTIR analysis was performed to examine the functional groups present in both the raw and acetylated samples, as well as to confirm the structural modifications resulting from acetylation. The FTIR spectra for RASAK and AASAK were captured using a Shimadzu 8400s FTIR spectrometer (Oxford model) over a range of 4000–400 cm⁻¹. To prepare the samples, a small amount of each material was finely ground with spectroscopic-grade KBr and subsequently pressed into a thin pellet using a hydraulic press. Observations were made regarding the appearance, disappearance, or shifts of characteristic peaks, which were analyzed to identify changes in functional groups due to acetylation. The increased intensity and the emergence of new peaks at elevated frequencies served as indicators of the incorporation of acetyl substituents, reflecting alterations in the surface chemistry of the raw material.

Surface morphology Study of RASAK and AASAK

The surface morphology of RASAK and AASAK was analyzed using a Scanning Electron Microscope (Phenom-World). To enhance conductivity and improve image resolution, the samples were sputter-coated with a thin layer of gold prior to imaging. The SEM was operated at an accelerating voltage of 15 kV, and micrographs were captured at various magnifications to examine the surface texture and porosity of the samples. The purpose of this analysis was to assess the physical changes resulting from the acetylation process, particularly concerning surface roughness, fragmentation, and pore development. It was anticipated that the unmodified RASAK would display a relatively dense and compact structure with limited surface porosity. Conversely, the acetylated AASAK was expected to exhibit a more fragmented and flaky morphology, showing increased surface roughness and a greater number of defined and enlarged pores. These morphological changes were critically analyzed to corroborate the enhanced oil sorption capacity of the modified biomass.

Physicochemical Properties / Proximate Analysis of ASAK

To assess the fundamental composition and suitability of the African Star Apple Kernel (ASAK) for chemical modification and crude oil sorption applications, we conducted a comprehensive series of physicochemical analyses. This included the extraction of non-structural components, as well as the determination of moisture, lignin, cellulose, and ash content.

Extraction of Water- and Ethanol-Soluble Extractives:

Before proceeding with acetylation, it was essential to remove non-structural materials such as waxes, fats, and oils that could interfere with subsequent chemical reactions. To accomplish this, 10.000 grams of sieved ASAK underwent Soxhlet extraction using a solvent, a mixture of n-hexane and acetone was maintained in a 4:1 (v/v) ratio for a duration of five hours. Following the extraction, the residue was oven-dried at 65 °C for 16 hours and subsequently stored in an airtight container for future use.

Determination of Moisture Content:

Moisture content was determined gravimetrically. A 2.000 g portion The specimen was accurately measured and placed into a dry, clean watch glass and placed in a drying oven at 105 °C for 24 hours. The sample was then removed, cooled in a desiccator, and reweighed. The percentage moisture content was calculated based on the weight loss after drying, indicating the amount of water originally present in the sample.

Determination of Lignin Content:

Lignin content was estimated using acid hydrolysis. A 2.000 g sample of ASAK was introduced into a 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask, followed by the addition of 15 mL of 72% H₂SO₄. The mixture was stirred at a rate of 24 revolutions per minute for a duration of two and a half hours at a temperature of 25 °C. using a temperature-controlled magnetic stirrer. Subsequently, 200 mL of deionized water was added, and the mixture was boiled for an additional 2 hours. After cooling for 24 hours, the mixture was transferred into a crucible and washed repeatedly with hot water until all traces of acid were removed. The recovered lignin residue was oven-dried at 105 °C, cooled in a desiccator, and weighed repeatedly until a constant mass was obtained.

Determination of Cellulose Content:

To determine the cellulose content, 2.000 g of ASAK was placed into a 100 mL beaker, and 10 mL of 4.375 mol·dm⁻³ NaOH was added for wetting. The mixture was stirred and transferred to a temperature-controlled magnetic stirrer, where 20 mL of the same NaOH solution was added at 5-minute intervals over a 30-minute period, maintaining the temperature at 20 °C. After adding 33 milliliters of deionized water, the solution was allowed to rest for a duration of sixty minutes. The resulting hemicellulose residue was filtered and washed sequentially with 100 mL of 2.075 mol·dm⁻³ NaOH, 200 mL of deionized water, and 15 mL of 10% acetic acid. The purified cellulose was oven-dried at 110 °C for 2 hours to a constant weight.

Determination Of Hemicellulose Content

A sample weighing one gram was placed into a 250-milliliter Erlenmeyer flask. To this, a 20 g/l sodium hydroxide solution was added to a volume of 150 milliliters. The mixture was then subjected to boiling with distilled water for a duration of three and a half hours. Upon cooling, the solution was filtered through vacuum filtration and adjusted until achieving a neutral pH. The resulting residue was dried in a conventional oven at 105°C until a constant weight was attained. The hemicellulose content was determined by calculating the difference in sample weight before and after this treatment.

Determination of Ash Content:

Ash content was determined according to the method outlined in reference [15]. A precise 2.000 g portion of the dried sample was carefully weighed into a pre-weighed porcelain crucible, which was subsequently placed in a muffle furnace that had been preheated to 600 °C. The sample underwent incineration for a duration of one hour. Following this, the crucible was allowed to cool in a desiccator before being reweighed. The weight difference recorded before and after ignition was utilized to compute the percentage ash content, reflecting the inorganic mineral residue present in the biomass.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Physicochemical Properties of RASAK

The physicochemical examination of the RASAK shed light on its structural characteristics and potential as a precursor for adsorbent materials. The moisture content of RASAK was measured at 9.74%, comfortably below the maximum permissible limit of 15% established by the Indonesian Industrial Standard (SII No. 0258-88). This relatively low moisture level suggests a lower risk of microbial degradation and enhanced storage stability, making RASAK an attractive option for sorption applications. The ash content was measured at 2.48%, reflecting a low level of inorganic residue. This is beneficial for adsorption applications, as a high ash content is typically correlated with decreased porosity and diminished efficiency of sorbents. Prior to acetylation, ethanol- and water-soluble extractives, mainly composed of waxes, oils, and fats, were effectively eliminated using Soxhlet extraction with a solvent mixture of acetone and n-hexane. The extractive content was found to be 14.25%, indicating the presence of non-structural hydrophobic materials, which could pose challenges for chemical modification if they are not adequately removed.

After the process of extractive removal, an analysis was conducted to determine the lignocellulosic composition of the biomass. The results indicated that the lignin content of the ASAK was 27.00%, reflecting a significant level of structural rigidity. In addition, the cellulose and hemicellulose contents were measured at 19.40% and 24.27%, respectively. These values reflect a balanced composition suitable for modification, particularly as cellulose provides the primary functional groups (hydroxyl groups) necessary for acetylation. The relatively high lignin content could also contribute to the mechanical stability of the modified material.

The findings highlight the critical role of pretreatment in improving the chemical reactivity and adsorption capacities of agricultural residues. The data collected correspond with previously reported values in the literature concerning lignocellulosic biomasses utilized in environmental remediation [18].

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopic Characterization

FTIR examination was performed to identify the functional groups in the Raw African Star Apple Kernel (RASAK) and to assess the alterations in the chemical structure following acetylation, resulting in the Acetylated African Star Apple Kernel (AASAK). The FTIR spectra for RASAK displayed significant peaks within the range of 3200–3500 cm^{-1} , indicative of free O–H stretch, which reveal the presence of hydroxyl groups, which are prevalent in cellulose and hemicellulose. A double peak located at 2919.52 cm^{-1} suggests C–H stretch originating from aliphatic hydrocarbons, while the peak at 2850.87 cm^{-1} corresponds to asymmetrical and symmetrical stretching of $-\text{CH}_2$ groups within cellulose and hemicellulose. Furthermore, the sharp absorption peak at 1744.39 cm^{-1} is associated with C=O stretch, indicating the presence of carbonyl groups from carboxylic acids, esters, or ketones [19]. The broad peak at 1625.95 was assigned to C=C stretching vibrations, characteristic of alkenes [19], [20]. 1331.05 cm^{-1} C–H bend, often found in lignin [21]. 1244.56 cm^{-1} was C–O stretching vibrations of the acetyl

group in lignin, esters or ethers or phenolic groups [22]. The strong absorption band at 1149.20 cm^{-1} is associated with the in-plane aromatic ring deformation vibrations [22]. 1074.84 cm^{-1} C-OH stretch which are common in lignocelluloses structures, alcohols and ethers [23], [24]. The strong peak at 997.13 cm^{-1} is indicative of C-H bond angle variations (bending), often found in alkanes or to $-\text{CH}_2$ rocking. The bands which appeared at 522.62 cm^{-1} is indicative of C-Cl stretching [25].

Figure 1 indicated there were absorptions at 3406.27 , 3361.53 , and 3310.43 cm^{-1} in AASAK. These were assigned to dimeric O-H stretch of hydrogen of OH, COOR and PHOH [26]. The absorption peaks at 568.13 and 517.71 cm^{-1} at the fingerprint region indicated the formation of C-H bend in terminal alkynes/C-Cl stretch/O-H out-of-plane stretch [27]. During the acetylation process, the bands initially observed on the surface of the precursor materials disappeared, leading to the emergence of new spectral bands. Notably, all newly formed bands, with the exception of those in the $3000\text{--}3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range, exhibited a shift to higher frequencies and demonstrated increased intensity.

After acetylation, the FTIR spectrum of AASAK exhibited significant changes. Notably, the intensity of the O-H band decreased markedly, suggesting the successful substitution of hydroxyl groups by acetyl groups. A new, more intense peak around 1745 cm^{-1} was observed, linked to the C=O stretch of COOR bonds formed during acetylation. Additionally, slight shifts in the fingerprint region ($1000\text{--}1300\text{ cm}^{-1}$), especially at 1230 cm^{-1} and 1025 cm^{-1} , confirmed changes in the C-O stretching vibrations due to acetylation. The spectral changes observed in the study clearly demonstrate that the acetylation process effectively modified the surface chemistry of ASAK. This alteration has resulted in an increase in hydrophobicity, enhancing its potential affinity for nonpolar substances, including crude oil. These modifications are consistent with previous research conducted on acetylated lignocellulosic materials [28].

Figure 1: FTIR spectra of RASAK and AASA

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) Morphology

The morphological characteristics of RASAK and AASAK were examined, this revealing notable differences arising from the chemical modification process. Figures 2, 3, and 4 illustrate the morphology of both RASAK and AASAK. The SEM micrographs of RASAK indicate a relatively dense and compact surface with minimal visible porosity and irregular roughness. This suggests that, while structurally intact, its less reactive nature may limit efficient adsorption due to a constrained surface area and reduced accessibility for sorbate molecules. In contrast, the SEM imagery of AASAK reveals significant surface fragmentation, a flaky texture, and larger, more defined pores. The observed increase in surface roughness and pore volume post-modification likely results from the disruption of cellulose and hemicellulose structures during the acetylation reaction. Such structural changes enhance the adsorptive surface area and improve the accessibility of active sites for interactions with crude oil components. The morphological transition from RASAK to AASAK effectively demonstrates the successful impact of the acetylation process in improving the structural features desirable for

adsorbent materials. Similar surface transformations following acetylation have been documented in other lignocellulosic materials, further affirming that chemical modification can significantly enhance the surface architecture of bio-based sorbents [29], [30].

Figure 2: SEM micrograph of RASAK (a) and, AASAK (b) at 50 μm and 1500 magnification

Figure 3 (a and b): SEM micrograph of RASAK (a) and, AASAK (b) at 80 μm and 1000x magnification

Figure 4: SEM micrograph of RASAK (a) and AASAK (b) at 150 μm and 500x magnification

From the SEM images it could be observed that for RASAK (a), the particle appeared compact with a rough surface texture and some visible pores or cavities. This indicated a dense structure with limited surface area (Figures 2a, 3a, and 4a). In contrast, the AASAK (b) exhibited a more fragmented structure characterized by a flakier appearance and larger, more pronounced pores or cavities. This finding aligns with previous studies [31], [32]. Consequently, it can be inferred that acetylation effectively enhanced the surface area and significantly improved the texture.

4. CONCLUSION

The research investigated the acetylation process of African Star Apple Kernels (*Chrysophyllum albidum*), highlighting its potential as a biomass material aimed at improving physicochemical properties for environmental applications. The primary objective of this study was to explore the structural and functional changes brought about by acetylation, as well as to assess the material's viability for environmental remediation tasks, particularly oil sorption. AASAK underwent a series of analyses to characterize the modified material comprehensively. This characterization included determining the chemical composition specifically the cellulose, lignin, ash, and moisture content. Additionally, Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy was utilized to examine the functional groups and chemical modifications of the kernel resulting from the acetylation process. The findings indicated a notable enhancement in the hydrophobicity of the acetylated material, a factor that is essential for effective oil sorption. The acetylation process markedly augmented the material's capability to absorb oil, positioning it as a viable candidate for environmental remediation efforts. This study also explored the material's prospects as a biodegradable alternative to synthetic oil sorbents, thereby contributing to the advancement of sustainable materials for environmental management. Through the acetylation of African Star Apple Kernels (*Chrysophyllum albidum*), improvements in their physicochemical properties were successfully achieved, particularly in terms of hydrophobicity and oil sorption capacity. FTIR spectroscopic analysis corroborated the alteration of functional groups, which is pivotal in enhancing the material's efficacy in oil sorption applications. These findings advocate for the potential application of acetylated African Star Apple Kernels as a sustainable and biodegradable solution designed for the remediation of oil spills, remediation and other environmental contexts. Moreover, the results suggest that acetylated African Star Apple Kernels present a promising alternative to traditional oil sorbents. Given their availability as a byproduct of the African Star Apple fruit, their large-scale application potential is further underscored. Future research endeavors may focus on refining the acetylation process and examining the material's long-term stability and effectiveness in addressing real-world environmental cleanup challenges.

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Conflict of interest/sponsorship

The authors declare that they have no known financial interests or personal relationships that may have appeared to influence the results presented in this paper.

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